

Composition and Stability of Citrate and Tartrate Complexes of Thallium(I)

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Conductometric and spectrophotometric studies on the composition and stability of the complexes formed between thallium (I) and citrate and tartrate ions have been made. A 1 : 1 (metal: ligand) complex is concluded to have been formed both for citrate and tartrate ligands, by monovariation and Job's continued variation methods. The dissociation constants of the complexes, determined by Job's method for non-equimolar solutions, are 15.3×10^{-4} and 40.96×10^{-3} at 28° for citrate and tartrate complexes, respectively.

The formation constant of thallos-citrate complex at zero ionic strength was determined by Schuffe and Agostino¹, but the composition of the complex was not established. Very few complexes of thallium (I) are reported in the literature. Sahu *et al.*² have studied 1:1 complex of thallium(I) with sulphosalicylate ion. Tartrate complex of monovalent thallium has not been tried so far. It was therefore thought worthwhile to make a complete study of composition and stability of citrate and tartrate complexes of thallium(I). Studies on thallos complexes with other substituted salicylic acids are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

E. Merck sample of thallos nitrate was prepared by accurately weighing and dissolving in double distilled water and gravimetrically estimated as chromate³. B. D. H. AnalaR samples of trisodium citrate and disodium tartrate were used as ligands.

For measurements of electrical conductance "Doron conductivity bridge" with 1000 cycle WTW oscillator and dip-type conductivity cell was used. Optical density measurements were made with the Beckman model DU quartz spectrophotometer, using 5 mm light path absorption cells.

All the mixtures were kept for about 6 hr. to attain the equilibrium. All the measurements were carried out at 28° ± 0.5°.

Procedure.—The composition of the complexes was established by monovariation method, using conductance property, and by Job's continued variation method⁴, using conductance and optical density as additive properties.

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1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 1623.

2. *This Journal*, 1962, **39**, 731.

3. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1953, p. 478.

4. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **x**, 9, 113.

The dissociation constants of the complexes were determined by Job's continued variation method⁴ for non-equimolar solutions, using conductance and absorbance as index properties. For the selection of ligand for accurate work, thalious nitrate solution was titrated against solutions of similar strength of citric acid, mono-, di-, and tri-sodium citrates with blanks for the metal and the ligand. The divergence in additive property was observed to be maximum in the case of trisodium citrate. Similarly the Δ -additive property was maximum in the case of disodium tartrate. For the present work therefore trisodium citrate and disodium tartrate were chosen as ligands.

Conductometric Study

Monovariation method was carried out with equimolar solutions of thalious nitrate with citrate and tartrate solutions. The volume of each mixture was kept constant (25 ml) by adding required volume of extra water to avoid the dilution error. A clear break was obtained where ratio of metal to ligand was 1:1 (Fig. 1). The composition of the complex was varied by Job's continued variation method⁴, using equimolar solutions. The total volumes of mixtures in each case were kept at 20 ml. The individual components were also diluted to the same extent as in the mixture. The conductances of these solutions were measured and Δ -conductance values were plotted against the percentage of the ligand (Fig. 2). In each case, maxima were obtained at 50% of the ligand which confirmed the formation of 1:1 complexes. (For both, citrate and the tartrate, the experiments were repeated for three different concentrations of equimolar solutions, but the Δ -values for only two were plotted to avoid overlapping with each other.)

Ligand added (ml) to 5 ml of $TlNO_3$.

FIG. 1

A = $M/30$ Metal + $M/30$ citrate.

B = $M/40$,, + $M/40$ tartrate.

% Ligand.

FIG. 2

A = $M/60$, B = $M/80$ equimol. metal and citrate soln.

A' = $M/40$, B' = $M/60$ equimol. metal and tartrate soln.

Job's method was also used for determination of the dissociation constant of the complexes. The experimental procedure was exactly the same as in the case for composition, the

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only difference being that the metal and ligand solutions used were non-equimolar. Maxima, which provide the value of x , are generally obtained by extrapolation (Fig. 3). (Three sets of mixtures were prepared but the results of only two are plotted).

FIG. 3

A = $M/60$, B = $M/100$ metal vs. $M/40$ citrate soln.

A' = $M/60$, B' = $M/80$ metal vs. tartrate soln.

The dissociation constant is calculated by the formula:

$$K = \frac{c[(p+1)x-1]^2}{(p-1)(1-2x)}$$

The average values of K for citrate and tartrate complexes are found to be 15.3×10^{-4} and 40.96×10^{-3} , respectively.

Spectrophotometric Study

Before actually working with any particular wave length, suitable wave lengths were selected where appreciable divergence from the additive value could be anticipated. Citrate complex was studied at wave lengths 255, 260, and 265 $m\mu$ and tartrate complex at 250, 255, and 260 $m\mu$.

For stoichiometry of the complex, $M/20$ thalious nitrate and $M/20$ ligand solutions were mixed in the same manner as in the conductometric study. Δ -optical density values were calculated at three different wave lengths. The graph of Δ -optical density vs. the % ligand shows maxima at the composition 1:1 (Fig. 4).

FIG. 4

A = 255 $m\mu$, B = 260 $m\mu$ equimol. metal and citrate soln.

A' = 250 $m\mu$, B' = 255 $m\mu$ equimol. metal and tartrate soln.

FIG. 5

A = 255 $m\mu$, B = 260 $m\mu$ metal/citrate soln.

A' = 250 $m\mu$, B' = 255 $m\mu$ metal/tartrate soln.

The dissociation constant of citrate and tartrate complexes were determined by mixing $M/50$ metal and $M/20$ ligand solutions. The mixing of the solutions was done in the same way as with conductometric work. Observations were recorded at three different wave lengths. The value of x was calculated after plotting Δ -O.D. against the % ligand and extrapolating the graph (Fig. 5).

The dissociation constants, calculated by this method, fairly agree with the values obtained by conductometric study.

Structure of the Complexes

The metal and the ligand solutions were mixed in equimolar ratios and after attainment of equilibrium, excess of nitron⁵ solution (prepared in 5% acetic acid) was added. The precipitate obtained was dried, weighed, and the amount of nitrate calculated. The calculated amount of nitrate was found to be equal to the theoretical value, indicating passivity of the nitrate ion in the complex formation.

In view of the conclusions of Pani and co-workers on citrate^{6,7} and malate⁸ complexes and of Bobtelsky and Jordan⁹ on tartrate complex, the possible structures of thallos-citrate and thallos-tartrate complexes are proposed as shown below:

The stability data reveal that thallos-citrate is more stable than thallos-tartrate, perhaps because two six-membered rings are formed in citrate complex (structure b).

5. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1953, p. 505.
6. Das and Pani, *this Journal*, 1955, **32**, 337.
7. Pattnaik and Pani, *ibid.*, 1957, **34**, 19.
8. Nanda and Pani, *ibid.*, 1956, **33**, 34.
9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1824.

whereas one five-membered and one six-membered rings are formed in tartrate complex. Six-membered ring imparts more stability than five-membered one. The structure (b) therefore seems to be more correct for thalious-citrate complex. The present investigation also concludes that the complex-forming nature of citric acid is more than that of tartaric acid.

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